

Lab tips, tricks and hacks:

Efficient and effective sample holding using Scotch 3M restickable tabs for laboratory experiments:

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Holding samples in place is important in a variety of experimental setups for a number of reasons. In many cases, the sample being tested must remain stationary in order for accurate measurements to be taken. If the sample is not held in place, it may move or shift during the experiment, leading to inaccurate or unreliable results. In addition, holding samples in place helps to ensure the safety of the sample and the individuals handling it. For example, if a sample is not secured properly, it may become damaged or break during the course of the experiment, potentially causing harm to the person handling it. Overall, the ability to effectively hold samples in place is crucial for conducting accurate and safe experiments in the laboratory.

There are several ways to hold samples in place in a laboratory setting. Vacuum chucks are a common method used in commercial experimental setups, but they can be difficult to implement in homebuilt systems. Double-sided tape is a widely used method in homebuilt setups, but it has several drawbacks, including the potential for adhesive residues and varying levels of adhesive strength. It is not uncommon to need to test several brands of double-sided tape until finding the one with the right level of adhesion strength.

In our laboratory, we use Scotch 3M restickable tabs ([see example here](#)) made of a viscoelastic material, similar to polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS), which adhere to surfaces through van der Waals forces, similar to how geckos stick to surfaces.

Figure 1. Pictures of the restickable tabs. (left) Picture of one of the packages containing the tabs. Note that there are slightly different packaging layouts. (center) Picture of one of the sheets (the package contains two) with the tabs. (right) Picture of one of the square tabs while the liner protective layer is being peeled off. The viscoelastic gel is sandwiched between two protective layers.

These tabs are convenient for holding samples in place in a variety of setups, including AFM, deterministic transfer, Raman, lithography, and spin coating.

Figure 2. Examples of use of the restickable tabs in our labs: deterministic transfer setup, spin-coating in an inexpensive spin-coater system without vacuum chuck and mounting the sample for atomic force microscopy study.

They are also capable of withstanding elevated temperatures, as they have been tested up to 200 degrees Celsius.

Figure 3. Using the restickable tabs to hold samples onto heaters. A SiO₂/Si sample is adhered to the surface of the heater of the deterministic transfer setup shown in Figure 2. The temperatures of the heater and the surface of the sample are measured at different heating powers finding that the restickable tabs sustain high temperature without degrading nor decreasing the adhesion strength. The thermal conductivity of the tabs is good enough to make the heating of samples possible up to 150 deg.

Lastly, we use these restickable tabs on a regular basis to secure samples in sample boxes without the need to use expensive specialized viscoelastic sample boxes. We use rather inexpensive plastic boxes (Modulor, [LINK](#), 0.64€ each) and we adhere small pieces of the Scotch restickable tabs to hold the samples in place.

Figure 4. Example of an inexpensive sample box securing the samples with restickable tabs.